

Happy 1st Year SMAUG!

Dear Readers,

Time has flown by for the SMAUG project, and before we knew it, we reached our first year of the project's implementation! 🎉

One intense and rewarding year kicked off in **October 2023 in Valencia** and closed its circle in **Heraklion, Crete, in October 2024**. Throughout these months, our project partners worked collaboratively to lay the foundations for the project's key outcomes. From the initial brainstorming sessions to the strategic planning and execution phases, we have successfully set the pillars for the project's future results, continuing as always to keep our project in the spotlight through communication and dissemination activities!

Sailing through calm waters, we are excited to continue our journey until we reach the final results of the SMAUG project.

Our 12 months Journey Reflection

YEAR 1

REFLECTIONS

We're excited to share a brief update on our journey so far, showcasing the progress and future activities of the SMAUG project. Twelve months filled with intense work, accomplishments, meetings, and technologies that wouldn't have materialised without our amazing partners!

Dive into our anniversary blog article and join the SMAUG journey

[Read more](#)

Let's hear our partner's thoughts on what is the most exciting part of the SMAUG project from our General Assembly meeting in Madrid!

Port of call: Latest news and events

From external events participation to project meetings, technological advancements and project insights. We have gathered the latest

SMAUG achievements in this section for your ease. Enjoy your reading!

SMAUG project at the EU Ports Alliance Workshop

The SMAUG project participated in the **European Ports Alliance workshop** in Brussels on the 12th of July 2024! SMAUG was invited to present its scope and aim at the workshop on Cluster IV, “Innovation: Use Innovative Technologies To Strengthen The Resilience Of Logistical Hubs And Shipping Sector To Drug Trafficking”.

[Read the full article here](#)

SMAUG 3rd General Assembly meeting

SMAUG hosted its 3rd General Assembly meeting on October 22-23 in Heraklion, Crete. The two-day event was organised by the [Heraklion Port Authority \(HPA\)](#). The General Assembly meeting provided an invaluable opportunity for SMAUG partners to meet in person, review the project's progress, and plan future activities.

Explore the GA meeting in Crete here!

In the GA meeting, emphasis was placed on the project's use cases. During the SMAUG's implementation, **three use case** scenarios will be executed, and their outcomes will be examined in a real port environment to ensure tight cooperation between end users and technical partners throughout the project's lifecycle.

At our last GA meeting, we interviewed partners from the ports where the use cases will be tested.

Watch the videos on our YouTube channel to reveal their answers. Don't forget to subscribe! 📺

SMAUG #Tech unveiled

We continue the **SMAUG Tech unveiled** series and proudly present **High-Resolution Sonar Inspection and Aerial Surveillance and Monitoring technologies.**

Learn everything about the technologies and their integration into the SMAUG project and have a clearer image with the pictures provided.

High-Resolution Sonar Inspection

Aerial Surveillance and Monitoring
technology

SMAUG Reading Corner

From deliverables to scientific publications, you can now explore all the SMAUG publications on our website!

[Read online here](#)

What's next?

The SMAUG project has successfully wrapped up its first year and continues to work towards achieving its goals and generating impactful results.

Stay tuned and join the SMAUG journey by following its social media profiles! 🚢

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